

Further work in this line to prepare some pure Guerbet's acid freed from the unsaturated impurities by ozonisation and the subsequent systematic examination of the pure compounds and its derivatives is in progress.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BANGALORE.

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STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART V. ISOLATION OF β -SANTALIC ACID, A NEW CONSTITUENT OF SANDALWOOD OIL

By S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

A new monobasic acid of the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ has been isolated from sandalwood oil. The substance contains two double bonds and consequently possesses a bicyclic structure and has been named β -santallic acid. The absorption spectra of the substance in the ultraviolet region have been investigated.

Among the different constituents of East Indian sandalwood oil which have so far been isolated (Simonsen, "Terpenes", Vol. II, p. 544) β -derivatives form a comparatively minor part. Except β -santalol and β -santalene all the other ingredients of the oil, so far isolated, are more or less connected with the tricyclic alcohol, α -santalol and its derivatives. About 4 g. of a new monobasic acidic substance of the molecular formula $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ have now been isolated from the East Indian sandalwood oil. As revealed by oxidation with percamphoric acid, the substance contains two double bonds and consequently possesses a bicyclic ring structure. In all probability the substance appears to be the corresponding carboxylic acid of β -santalol and has therefore been named β -santallic acid. It is necessary to mention in this connection that the acid is an unknown substance and though β -santalol can be isolated in a pure state it has not been possible up till now, to prepare β -santallic acid from it. The preparation involves about 5 successive synthetic operations necessitating the use of a considerable amount of β -santalol which it is difficult to procure. A comparative study of this substance and its derivatives with those of α -santallic acid has been made. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Name	Boiling point.	Difference in boiling point.	n_D^{20} .	Difference in n_D^{20} .
α -Santalol	155°/9 mm. }	38°	1.5037 }	0.0018
α -Santallic acid	193°/9 mm. }		1.5055 }	
Me- α -santalate	147°/9 mm. }	46°	1.4910 }	0.0145
β -Santalol	163°/9 mm. }	39°	1.5120 }	0.0016
New acid	202°/9 mm. }		1.5136 }	
Me-ester of new acid	157°/9 mm. }	45°	1.4989 }	0.0147

Thus, it is seen that the relationship existing between the boiling points and refractive indices of α -santalol, α -santallic acid and its methyl ester is quite analogous to that existing between β -santalol, the new acid and its methyl ester. It is also well known that the β -deri-

vatives of the santalol series contain two double bonds and consequently higher refractive indices than the corresponding compounds of the α -series, all of which contain only one ethylenic linkage. As shown in Table II, the difference between the values of the refractive indices of the santalols, santalic acids and their methyl esters is almost identical. This proves that there exists an additional double bond in the new acid.

TABLE II

Name	n_D^{20}	Change in n_D^{20}
α -Santalol	1.5037	0.0083
β -Santalol	1.5120	
α -Santalic acid	1.5055	0.0080
New acid	1.5135	
Me- α -santalate	1.4909	0.0080
Me-ester_of new acid	1.4989	

As stated before, oxidation with percamphoric acid reveals the existence of two double bonds in the new acid. The absorption spectrum of the substance in the ultraviolet region has also been investigated. The substance shows strong absorption as indicated from the stiff nature of the curve. In conformity with the structure of β -santalol (Ruzicka, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1935, 18, 1835), the following structure has been suggested for the new acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation.—The acid was isolated from fraction C (*vide* Part IV). The small amount of higher boiling liquid, which was obtained after redistillation of Guerbet's acid, was mixed with the fraction C. The total amount (about 7 g.) was then fractionated thrice from a 10 c.c. Claisen's flask to which a 12 cm. bulb-fractionating column had been fused. The portion coming at $181^\circ/1$ mm. was collected. Yield 4 g. from 7 lbs. of oil (Found: C, 76.41; H, 9.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$

requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46 per cent.) B.P. $181^{\circ}/1$ mm.; $202^{\circ}/9$ mm.; $n_D^{28.5}$, 1.5100; n_D^{10} , 1.5136; unsaturation number, 1.90. The substance is thick and syrupy in nature and insoluble in water. It smells exactly like Guerbet's acid. The silver salt is insoluble in water and is fairly stable towards light at ordinary temperature.

This is a weak acid and cannot be correctly titrated with alkali. Equivalent weight was found by ignition of the silver salt. (Found: Equiv., 233.9 $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires Equiv., 234.49).

Methyl ester $C_{15}H_{21}O_2$ (CH_3) was prepared from the silver salt and methyl iodide in the usual way; b.p. $157^{\circ}/9$ mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.4969; n_D^{20} , 1.4989. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 9.77. $C_{15}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 77.38; H, 9.7 per cent).

Absorption spectrum was determined by following the same procedure as in the case of Guerbet's acid (*cf.* Part IV).

Further work for the complete elucidation of the structure of this compound is in progress.

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STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART VI. A NOTE ON THE PARACHOR OF FUSED RING STRUCTURE

By P. C. GUHA AND S. C. BHATTACHARYYA

Only a limited amount of work has been done about the parachor of compounds containing fused ring structures with some of the carbon atoms being common to more than one ring. Deshapande and others (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 157) by using *isonitrosocamphor* in nitrobenzene solution have proved the additive nature of parachor in fused-ring compounds.

Substances more complicated than *isonitrosocamphor* are easily obtainable among the compounds of the santalol series. In connection with our researches in the santalol series, the parachor of a typical compound of this series *viz.* that of the methyl ester of *tricyclo-ekasantalic acid* has been determined. The substance possesses a fused tricyclic ring structure and is a liquid under ordinary conditions. The pure ester was prepared according to the method of Semmler (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1120, 1124), b.p. $127^{\circ}/10$ mm.; n_D^{20} , 1.4785; d_4^{20} , 1.0166; Molecular formula $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$; Mol. Wt. 208.29. Surface tension of the substance was determined by the drop method, Traube's stalagmometer being used for this purpose, pure bi-distilled water was used as the reference liquid. Density of the ester at different temperatures was determined with a very small pycnometer; parachor was calculated in the usual way.

Temp.	Surface tension of ester.	Mol. Wt.	Density.	Parachor (P)	Mean (P)
20°	34.59	208.29	1.0166	407.7	497.0
30°	33.47	208.26	1.00737	496.3	